

Nitromethane as Polar Solvent: Part II. Acid-Base Neutralisation Reactions in Nitromethane

Ram Chand Paul, Raj Kaushal and Survinder Singh Pahil

Acid-base neutralisation reactions between nitrogen bases, tertiary bases and antimony(V), antimony (III), arsenic(III), iron (III), tin (IV), tellurium (IV) and titanium(IV) chlorides and fluorosulphuric and sulphuric acids in nitromethane have been studied conductometrically, and explained on the basis of the autoionisation of nitromethane as : $2\text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{CH}_3\text{NO}_2\text{H}^+ + \text{CH}_2\text{NO}_2^-$
This process of neutralisation has been confirmed by isolation of products which have been found to contain molecules of nitromethane.

In part I of this series¹, autoionisation of nitromethane has been proposed as

and the nature of the Lewis acids, protonic acids and organic tertiary bases has also been discussed. In the present communication, the neutralisation reactions between nitrogen tertiary bases and Lewis as well as protonic acids in nitromethane have been studied conductometrically and the neutralisation products characterised.

Nitromethane (Hn) as solvent reacts with acidic and basic species as follows :

where A is the monobasic Lewis acid such as arsenic(III) chloride, antimony (III) chloride, antimony (V) chloride and iron (III) chloride and B is a monoacid base like pyridine, quinoline, α -picoline and dimethylaniline.

In case of dibasic Lewis acids (A_2) such as tin (IV), titanium (IV) and tellurium (IV) chlorides, the reactions may be described as

The neutralisation reactions have been followed conductometrically at 28° and the results are given in Figures 1-9. When the solution of antimony(V) chloride, antimony (III) chloride, arsenic (III) chloride or iron (III) chloride in nitromethane is added to solution of an organic tertiary base (Figs 1-9), there is rise in conductance till acid-base molar ratio 1 : 1 is reached. Further addition of acid solution causes an increase in conductance but the rate of increase is entirely different which indicates the change of ionic species at 1 : 1 molar ratios.

The neutralisation may be represented as follows :

FIG. I CONDUCTOMETRIC TITRATIONS OF VARIOUS BASES WITH ANTIMONY V CHLORIDE IN NITRO METHANE AT 28°C.

FIG. 2 CONDUCTOMETRIC TITRATIONS OF VARIOUS BASES WITH ANTIMONY III CHLORIDE IN NITROMETHANE AT 28°C.

A similar situation is also encountered when monoprotonic acids such as fluoro-sulphuric acid are titrated against organic bases in nitromethane (Fig. 8). However, their mode of reaction which is slightly different from that of the Lewis acids and the neutralisation reaction may be represented as

Conductometric titration of tin(IV) and tellurium(IV) chlorides with organic bases (Figs. 5, 6) exhibit a break in the curve at 1:1 acid-base molar ratio indicating the possibility that tin(IV) chloride may act as monobasic acid in nitromethane and only one proton is released.

The reaction may be represented as follows :

However, the situation with titanium(IV) chloride is quite different where two breaks are obtained at base/acid molar ratio 1:1 and 2:1 (Fig. 7) indicating that it acts as a dibasic acid. In this case, the base has been used as titrant as concentrated solution of titanium(IV) chloride in nitromethane could not be prepared due to separation of the adduct. The neutralisation reaction is similar to the earlier ones except that a disolvate is partially produced and from this two protons are released.

FIG 3 CONDUCTOMETRIC TITRATIONS OF VARIOUS BASES WITH ARSENIC III CHLORIDE IN NITROMETHANE AT 28°C

FIG 4 CONDUCTOMETRIC TITRATIONS OF VARIOUS BASES WITH IRON III CHLORIDE IN NITROMETHANE AT 28°C.

The conductometric titrations of sulphuric acid against organic tertiary bases in nitromethane (Fig. 9) show two breaks at acid base molar ratio 0.5 : 1 and 1 : 1 as is expected from the dibasic nature of the acid. The reactins may be represented as follows:

FIG 5 CONDUCTOMETRIC TITRATIONS OF VARIOUS BASES WITH TIN IV CHLORIDE IN NITROMETHANE AT 28°C.

FIG. 6 CONDUCTOMETRIC TITRATIONS OF VARIOUS BASES WITH TELLURIUM IV CHLORIDE IN NITROMETHANE AT 28°C.

so that both acid and normal salts are formed.

The salts formed during the course of reaction were isolated, purified and analysed. The analytical results obtained are given in Table I and are in agreement with the above observations.

FIG. 7 CONDUCTOMETRIC TITRATIONS OF VARIOUS BASES WITH TITANIUM IV CHLORIDE IN NITROMETHANE AT 28°C.

FIG. 8 CONDUCTOMETRIC TITRATIONS BETWEEN FLUORE SULPHURIC ACID & VARIOUS BASES IN NITROMETHANE AT 28°C.

EXPERIMENTAL

Nitromethane¹, Lewis acids², protonic acids^{3,4} and nitrogen tertiary bases² were prepared and/or purified according to the procedures reported in literature.

FIG. 9 CONDUCTOMETRIC TITRATIONS BETWEEN SULPHURIC ACID & VARIOUS BASES IN NITROMETHANE AT 28°C.

1. R. C. Paul, R. Kaushal and S. S. Pahil, this Journal, 1965, **42**, 483.
2. R. C. Paul, K. C. Malhotra and O. C. Vaidya, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1965, **3**, 1.
3. R. C. Paul, K. C. Malhotra and K. C. Khanna, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1965, **3**, 63.
4. R. C. Paul, S. K. Vasisht, K. C. Malhotra and S. S. Pahil, *Anal. Chem.*, 1962, **34**, 820.

Conductometric titrations were carried out according to the procedure described earlier².

TABLE 1

Acid-base neutralisation complexes in nitromethane

S. No.	Acid	Base	Complex	Colour	m.p. 0°C	Analysis			
						Metal Reqd.	Found	Chloride or Sulphur Reqd.	Found
1.	Sulphuric acid	Quinoline	$H_2S=O_4C_9H_7N.CH_3NO_2$	White	161	—	—	11.11	11.02
2.	Fluorosulphuric acid	,,	$HSO_3FC_9H_7N(CH_3NO_2)_2$	,,	82	—	—	9.11	9.00
3.	Tin (IV) chloride	,,	$SnCl_4C_9H_7N.CH_3NO_2$	,,	75	26.32	36.13	31.55	31.28
4.	Tin (IV) chloride	Pyridine	$SnCl_4C_5H_5N.CH_3NO_2$	,,	198	28.00	27.86	35.52	35.76
5.	Tin (IV) chloride	α -Picoline	$SnCl_4C_6H_7N.CH_3NO_2$	,,	65	28.50	28.26	34.30	34.45
6.	Titanium (IV) chloride	Pyridine	$TiCl_4(C_5H_5N)_2(CH_3NO_2)_2$	Yellowish brown	62	10.21	10.04	30.21	29.91
7.	Titanium (IV) chloride	Quinoline	$TiCl_4(C_9H_7N)_2CH_3NO_2$	,,	Above 220	9.61	9.52	27.90	27.61
8.	Titanium (IV) chloride	Dimethyl-aniline	$TiCl_4C_6H_5N(CH_3)_2(CH_3NO_2)_2$	Dark brown.	175	8.66	8.54	25.63	25.40
9.	Titanium chloride	α -Picoline	$TiCl_4(C_6H_7N)_2(CH_3NO_2)_2$	Black	...	9.64	9.46	28.51	18.19
10.	Antimony (V) chloride	Pyridine	$SbCl_5C_5H_5N.CH_3NO_2$	Light orange	85	27.73	27.58	40.34	39.92
11.	Antimony (V) chloride	Quinoline	$SbCl_5C_9H_7N.CH_3NO_2$	Light red	129	24.90	24.71	36.23	35.95
12.	Antimony (V) chloride	α -Picoline	$SbCl_5C_5H_7NCH_3NO_2$	Chocolate brown	Above 220	26.87	26.52	39.10	38.83
13.	Antimony (V) chloride	Dimethyl-aniline	$SbCl_5(C_6H_5N(CH_3)_2CH_3NO_2)$	Black	149	25.31	25.04	36.92	36.52
14.	Antimony (III) chloride	Pyridine	$SbCl_3C_5H_5N.CH_3NO_2$	White	132	33.11	32.11	28.90	28.59
15.	Antimony (III) chloride	Quinoline	$SbCl_3C_9H_7N.CH_3NO_2$	Light yellowish brown	180	29.15	28.82	25.45	25.18
16.	Arsenic (III) chloride	α -Picoline	$AsCl_3C_6H_7N.CH_3NO_2$	Reddish brown	Above 220	22.35	22.01	31.74	31.28
17.	Arsenic (III) chloride	Dimethyl aniline	$AsCl_3(C_6H_5N(CH_3)_2CH_3NO_2)$	White	Above 220	20.63	20.42	29.30	29.02

The neutralisation complexes were prepared by slowly adding ice-cold solution of the acid to that of base in nitromethane with constant stirring under dry conditions. The crystalline product, thus separated out, was filtered, washed with carbon tetrachloride and dried under vacuum.